

Thermal and Emission Evaluation of Single Cylinder Diesel Engine Using Waste Palm Cooking Oil Extracted Biodiesel

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Abstract:

The major reason for global warming is emission of gases from engines and at the same time to overcome fuel crisis is challenging task and one better solution for such issues is biodiesel extracted from waste cooking oil, which not only reduces fuel requirement of engine but also reduces carbon monoxide and NO_x emission at greater extend. The objective of present research paper is represent the thermal and emission performance of biodiesel extracted from waste cooking palm oil and blended 10, 20 and 30 % in standard diesel as a fuel.

Introduction

Compression ignition (CI) engines have been used in the industrial and agricultural sectors, and in construction, power factories, and transportation, for several decades. This broad use has resulted in a growing demand for petroleum-based diesel. However, global fossil-fuel reserves have become limited due to rising fuel prices, depleting petroleum reserves and issues related to atmospheric pollution. As a result, many researchers have concentrated on the discovery of renewable, carbon-neutral, and environmentally-friendly non-petroleum-based diesel in recent years. Biodiesel is produced from various feedstocks, such as rapeseed, soybean, cottonseed oil, palm oil, and jojoba oil, and can be used to fuel internal combustion engines with no significant difference from petroleum-based fuels. Since most biodiesel is manufactured using edible oils, the price of biodiesel is higher than conventional diesel. This is a significant barrier to the commercialization of biodiesel. The use of edible feedstocks could also intensify the competition between fuel supply and food production on agricultural land, increasing the cost of food and oil. As such, low-priced, inedible feedstock-based fuels, such as waste cooking oil synthetic diesel, should be adopted due to their competitive pricing compared to conventional diesel, and to ensure food security worldwide. The use of feedstock-based fuels can also help to lessen environmental issues by reducing waste-oil disposal. Hoi Nguyen et. al [1] evaluated and compared the influence of waste cooking oil synthetic diesel with that of commercial diesel fuel on an engine's operating characteristics. Waste cooking oil based biodiesel can be used to fuel conventional CI engines, because it allows the engine to work well and to operate smoothly at all operation conditions. Mohamed F et.al [2] used methyl ester of waste cooking oil (MEWCO) and blended in 10, 20 and 100 % with diesel and investigated thermal emission performance. Mixing 20% MEWCO is the best compromise, mixing ratio and beyond that, dramatic reduction in the outcome of the performance has been observed. İlker Örs [3] studied effect of adding bioethanol produced from sugar beet and biodiesel produced from waste cooking oils in diesel in with each

other in the volumetric rates to be 20% and 80%. The brake-specific fuel consumption increases and brake thermal efficiency decreases. Gabriel Galván Muciño et. al [4] focused on the catalytic performance of sea sand as a nonconventional catalyst in the transesterification reaction of used cooking oil and refined oil with methanol. The sea sand was utilized as a source of calcium oxide. Saumitra Mishra et.al [5] investigated effect of effect of Peroxides (DTBP) and alcohol (ethanol) based additives are on waste

cooking oil biodiesel results showed a maximum reduction in NOX, CO, HC and smoke concentrations are 13, 30, 43 and 45% respectively. Hasan Maksum et.al [6] carried out experimentation using waste cooking oil based biodiesel as blending fuel with standard diesel and results show reduction in torque, power, thermal efficiency while specific fuel consumption increases.

Experimentation

In the present research work is divided into two parts: 1) Extraction of biodiesel from waste PAM cooking oil 2) Experimentation in single cylinder diesel engine by blending biodiesel in 10, 20 and 30 % extracted from waste PAM cooking oil proposition with diesel.

1) Extraction of Biodiesel from Waste PAM cooking oil

The waste cooking oil of 250ml is heated at 60 °C to remove moisture content in heating mantle. After which NaOH is added into 160 ml of methanol and heated separately. In the next process after 15 minutes both solutions are mix in a beaker. There afterwards the mixture is stirred (800-1000 rpm) and continues for about 25-30 minutes, then after 30 minutes the mixture is transferred into a separating flask and shake thoroughly and allow the mixture the mixture to get settle down for 24 hrs at room temperature so the glycerine and crude biodiesel get separated. After which collect the biodiesel in separate conical flask and add amount of water into the conical flask and shake thoroughly and leave the conical flask to settle and removes the water.

Fig. 1 Raw PAM oil, Waste Cooking PAM oil and Biodiesel extracted from Waste Cooking PAM oil

2) Experimentation in single cylinder diesel engine by blending biodiesel in 10, 20 and 30 % extracted from waste PAM cooking oil proposition with diesel

Engine and Dynamometer Specifications:

Compression ratio	18
Fuel	Diesel
No.of cylinder	4
Bore Diameter	87.50 mm
Stroke length L	110 mm
Connecting road	234 mm
Swept volume	661.45 cc
Cooling	Water
Speed	1500
Rated Power	3.5 kw
Starting	Electric
Dynamometer type	Eddy current dynamometer

In experimental set up to start the engine with the ignition starter switch the fuel tank is filled with blended diesel and by adjusting compression ratio and speed of an engine to obtain emission, combustion and performance characteristics of extracted biodiesel from waste cooking pam oil blended 10%, 20%, and 30% with diesel in single cylinder compression ignition with five loading conditions (no load, 25%, 50%, 75% and 100%), In the present work engine speed and compression ratio are maintained at 1500 RPM and 18 respectively.

Fig. 2 Schematic Diagram of Experimental set up

Result and Discussion

Table: 1
Property of Diesel and Waste Palm seed Extracted Biodiesel

Name of Property	Unit	ASTM Standard	Diesel	Waste Palm Seed Biodiesel
Density	Kg/m ³	D287	816	866
Kinematic Viscosity @40 ^o c	cSt	D445	2.09	2.89
Calorific Value	Calorie/gm- ^o C	D4809	10236	10017
Flash Point	^o C	D93-58T	53	155
Fire Point	^o C	D93-58T	56	162

(a): HC ppm

(b): CO % Volume

(c) NO_x ppm

(d) Smoke

(e) CO₂ % Volume

Fig 3 (a, b, c, d, e) Emission Characteristics

(a) Indicated Power

(b) Break Power

(c) Indicated Thermal efficiency

(d) Mechanical efficiency

(e) Specific Fuel Consumption

Fig 4 (a, b, c, d, e) Thermal Performance Characteristics

Figure 3 and Figure 4 represent emission and performance characteristics of blended biodiesel extracted from waste cooking pam oil with diesel. From Fig 3 it is clear that with increases in load the CO_2 and NO_x emission increase sharply and rise in HC and CO is gradual. In case of 20 % blending increment in CO and HC are low compare to 10 % and 30 % blending but rise in the CO_2 and NO_x is real threaten for use waste pam cooking based biodiesel as fuel.

In case of Figure 4 break power increases consistently with an increase in percentage blending but at the same time specific fuel consumption based on break power is high at low load and is overlapped over diesel at high load but in the moderate limit of fuel consumption. The mechanical efficiency is almost parallel and is overlapped over diesel at low load and reduces slightly at high loads Indicated power and indicated thermal efficiency varying continuously with increases in load in case of diesel as well as in case of blending also.

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